

Cybersecurity in the Electrical Power and Energy System (EPES) with Software-Defined Network Architecture SDN MicroSENSE

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The digital infrastructure that supports the power grid plays an increasingly important role. A digital power system provides new opportunities for system operations and regional cooperation. The information and communication architecture should enable cybersecurity and ensure confidentiality, integrity and availability in data exchange.

Software-Defined Network

Software-Defined Network (SDN) is a network architecture which decouple network control and forwarding functions, enabling network control to become directly programmable. The aim of SDN is to provide open interfaces that enable the development of software that can control the connectivity, along with possible inspection and modification of traffic that may be performed in the network. In SDN network intelligence is logically centralized in SDN controller that maintain a global view of the network. The SDN controller is a logically centralized entity in charge of translating the requirements from the SDN applications down to the infrastructure and providing the SDN applications with an abstract view of the network. SDN greatly simplifies the network devices themselves, since they no longer need to understand and process routing protocols, but merely accept instructions from the SDN controllers. Figure 1 depicts a logical view of the SDN architecture and its layers [1].

Figure 1. SDN basic components

According to Open Network Foundation (ONF) basic components of SDN architecture are [2]:

- Data plane - comprises network elements, which expose their capabilities toward the SDN controller (control plane) via interfaces southbound from the controller.
- Controller plane - comprises a set of SDN controllers, each of which has exclusive control over a set of resources exposed by one or more network elements in the data plane.
- Application plane - comprises one or more applications, each of which has exclusive control of a set of resources exposed by one or more SDN controllers. Additional interfaces to applications are not precluded. An application may invoke or collaborate with other applications.
- Management plane - each application, SDN controller and network element has a functional interface to a manager.

On both sides of the interface between network infrastructure devices and the SDN control plane is implemented OpenFlow protocol. The OpenFlow uses the concept of flows to identify network traffic based on pre-defined match rules that can be statically or dynamically programmed by the SDN control plane. It also

allows application plane to define how traffic should flow through network devices based on parameters such as policy rules, security applications, or other resources. Since OpenFlow allows the network to be programmed on a per-flow basis, an OpenFlow-based SDN architecture provides extremely granular control, enabling the network to respond to real-time changes at the application level. Between the SDN control plane and application plane are implemented application programming interfaces (APIs). Thus, with APIs between the SDN control and application layers, different business applications can operate and manage the network [3].

SDN and cybersecurity

Controllers collect traffic flow information from all network devices connected and thus have complete visibility into the users, devices and applications on the network. Anomaly detection can be successfully applied to traffic flows in order to identify different kinds of attack that can severely degrade smart grid availability. Controller APIs enable programmatic two-way interaction between the network and external security applications. These external programs instruct the controller how to reprogram devices to take mitigating actions in case of cyberattack [4].

SDN-MicroSENSE in detection and mitigation of cyberattacks

The SDN paradigm can bring new opportunities to enhance security of power grid communication and SCADA/EMS networks, offering new approaches for preventing, detecting and mitigating cyberattacks. Based on this reality, the SDN-microSENSE project intends to provide a set of secure, privacy-enabled and resilient to cyberattacks tools, thus ensuring the normal operation of EPES. In particular, adopting an SDN-based technology, SDN-microSENSE will develop a three-layer security architecture, by deploying and implementing risk assessment processes, self-healing capabilities, large-scale distributed detection and prevention mechanisms, as well as an overlay privacy protection framework. Electricity system operator together with 30 other organizations participates in the implementation of the project

Basically, the main concept consists of intermittent network statistics collection from the network data plane and application of classification algorithms on those statistics in order to detect any anomalies. If an anomaly is detected, the application plane instructs the controllers how to reprogram the data plane to mitigate the cyberattack. In the application plane of SDN MicroSENSE, there are components responsible for malicious network flows that should be isolated, considering the results of tools for deep flow inspection, combining statistical analysis and machine learning mechanisms [5].

Cross-Layer Security Information and Event Management (XL-SIEM)

XL-SIEM system is a part of the main component of the SDN-MicroSENSE project. XL-SIEM is ultrafast logging tool for real time collection and analysis of security events. SIEM Agents, which are distributed in the infrastructure plane, provide data collection [6]. The SIEM Agent is a software capable of processing events from different data sources – network switches, routers, firewalls and RTUs. Events are generated by SNMP, Syslog and Netflow or acquired from devices (sensors) connected to a mirror port of a network switch. After the collection the events are securely sent to the XL-SIEM engine via Transport layer security (TLS), where they are processed and correlated (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Security events collection by XL-SIEM

Then the DiscØvery tool will provide appropriate visualisation cyberattacks and possible abnormal behaviours [7]. The produced visualizations will be clear

enough for the security administrators to identify cyberattacks patterns, reveal hidden correlation and predict new security issues.

Conclusion

SDN architecture may enable, facilitate or enhance security applications due to the controller's central view of the network, and its capacity to reprogram the data plane at any time. By correlating events seen on the network, different network attacks classified by their volume such as Distributed Denial of Service, Brute Force attempts, worm propagation or different types of network scans could be detected and mitigated. As part of an ongoing research, SDN MicroSENSE will implement and validate its approach to develop innovative applications which exploit direct networking controllability and programmability offered by SDN for achieving resilient and secure operations in the face of various cyber threats and failures.

References

1. SDN Architecture. Open Networking Foundation. Palo Alto, CA. 2014.
Accessed on: June, 2014. [online].
Available:https://www.opennetworking.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/02/TR_SDN_ARCH_1.0_06062014.pdf
2. SDN Architecture Overview. Open Networking Foundation. Palo Alto, CA. 2013. Accessed on: December, 2013. [online]. Available:
<https://www.opennetworking.org/images/stories/downloads/sdn-resources/technical-reports/SDN-architecture-overview-1.0.pdf>
3. Software-Defined Networking: The New Norm for Networks. Open Networking Foundation. Palo Alto, CA. 2012. Accessed on: April, 2012. [online]. Available:
<https://www.opennetworking.org/images/stories/downloads/sdn-resources/white-papers/wp-sdn-newnorm.pdf>
4. Jung, O., Smith, P., Magin, J. and Reuter, L. Anomaly Detection in Smart Grids based on Software Defined Networks. Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Smart Cities and Green ICT Systems (SMARTGREENS 2019), p.157-164.
5. SDN MicroSENSE Project. Horizons-EU 2020. 2019.

6. Gonzalez-Granadillo G., Gonzalez-Zarzosa S. and Faiella M. Towards an Enhanced Security Data Analytic Platform. 15th International Joint Conference on Security and Cryptography (2018).
7. Github. DiscØvery-CyberLens Software Tool. Availale: <https://github.com/CyberLens/Discovery>. Last accessed 2020.